

TECHNOLOGY IS AN EFFECTIVE TOOL IN TEACHING

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Annotation: This article gives information about the role of using new technologies in learning English as a second/foreign language. It discussed different attitudes which support English language learners to increase their learning skills through using technologies.

Key words: technologies, language learning , use

Technology is an effective tool for learners. Learners must use technology as a significant part of their learning process. Teachers should model the use of technology to support the curriculum so that learners can increase the true use of technology in learning their language skills . Learners' cooperation can be increased through technology. Cooperation is one of the important tools for learning. Learners cooperatively work together to create tasks and learn from each other through reading their peers' work. There are some important issues pertinent to the use of technology in language learning. The literature review indicated that technology resources cannot guarantee teachers' teaching and learners' learning. Teachers should be convinced of the usefulness and advantages of technology in improving learners' learning. This means that teachers need support and training for integrating technology into language teaching. The review revealed that when technology is used appropriately, it can bring about a lot of advantages to teachers and learners. It is a resource that can be used by learners because it helps them solve their learning problems and find methods to use what they have learnt in ways that are effective and meaningful. In addition, the review literature indicated that the use of technologies plays a key role in language learning based on their own pace, helps in self-understanding, does not stop interaction with the teacher, and creates high motivation in learners for the effective learning of language skills. Furthermore, the paper represented that learners should use technology to enhance their language skills because it has as a crucial role in developing learners' creativity and provides them with interesting, enjoyable, and exciting alternatives to study the language. To sum up, the findings of this literature review showed that technology provides interaction between teachers and learners, provides comprehensible input and output, helps learners to develop thinking skills,

makes learning and teaching becomes more student -centered, promotes learners' autonomy and helps them feel more confident, and increases learners' motivation to effectively learn a foreign language. Technology -enhanced teaching environment is more effective than lecture -based class. Teachers should find methods of applying technology as a useful learning instrument for their learners although they have not learnt technology and are not able to use it like a computer expert. The application of technology has considerably changed English teaching methods. It provides so many alternatives as making teaching interesting and more productive in terms of advancement. In traditional classrooms, teachers stand in front of learners and give lecture, explanation, and instruction through using blackboard or whiteboard. These method must be changed concerning the development of technology. The usage of multimedia texts in classroom assists learners in become familiar with vocabulary and language structures. The application of multimedia also makes use of print texts, film, and internet to enhance learners' linguistic knowledge. The use of print, film, and internet gives learners the chance to collect information and offers them different materials for the analysis and interpretation of both language and contexts.

In the following section, the researcher presents some recommendations for learners to improve their language skills through using technology:

1. Teachers should implement a technology plan that considers integration strategies along with purchasing decisions.
2. Professional development should be specifically considered in order to assure learners' learning and to change the attitudes of teachers unfamiliar with the advantages that technology provides .
3. The technology plan must be closely aligned with the curriculum standards. Teachers should know what educational approach is the most effective one when integrating technologies in the classroom.
4. The computer technology is an integral part of the learning activity through which skills are transferred to learners.
5. Language teachers should urge their learners to use technology in developing their language skills.
6. Universities should regard technology as a significant part of teaching and learning programs.
7. Technology experts should provide extra assistance for teachers who use it in teaching their English courses.
8. Teachers should be a pattern for their learners in using computer technology

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9. Teachers should create technology -integrated lesson materials. These materials should concentrate on teaching and learning, not just on technology issues.

10. Teachers should find the ways that technology can help them towards learner -centered instruction as opposed to teacher -centered instruction.

11. Teachers should be aware of their roles as guides and facilitators of their learners' learning.

12. In order to facilitate the integration of technology, enough support and technical assistance should be provided for teachers.

13. Training should be provided for teachers to learn how to use and teach it effectively.

14. Teachers should seek the guidance from their colleagues who can help them teach better through using technology.

Technology has always been an important part of teaching and learning environment. It is an essential part of the teachers' profession through which they can use it to facilitate learners' learning. When we talk about technology in teaching and learning, the word 'integration' is used. With technology being part of our everyday lives, it is time to rethink the idea of integrating technology into the curriculum and aim to embed technology into teaching to support the learning process. That is to say, technology becomes an integral part of the learning experience and a significant issue for teachers, from the beginning of preparing learning experiences through to teaching and learning process.

References:

1. Kurbanovna, A. N. (2024). ISSUES OF LEARNING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE AT A HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION. Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, 11(06), 269-270.
2. Aliqulova, M. (2024). АНАЛИЗ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ЯЗЫКА И СТИЛЯ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЙ АИ КУПРИНА. О 'ЗБЕК TILINING XORIJDA O 'QITILISHI: TA'LIM NAZARIYASI VA AMALIYOTI, 1(01), 82-87.
3. Алиқулова, М. Ш. (2023). ЛЕКСИКО-СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАССКАЗОВ АЛЕКСАНДРА КУПРИНА. Центральноеазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 2(12 Part 2), 172-174.
4. Bazarova, D. (2024). TA'LIM RUS TILIDA OLIB BORILADIGAN GURUHLARDA "O 'ZBEK TILIDA SO 'Z TARKIBI" MAVZUSINI O 'RGATISH TAJRIBASIDAN. O 'ZBEK TILINING XORIJDA O 'QITILISHI: TA'LIM NAZARIYASI VA AMALIYOTI, 1(01), 88-90.
5. Bazarova, D. B. (2023). ON THE USE OF ALTERNATIVE WORDS. American Journal Of Philological Sciences, 3(05), 48-51.

6. Аликулова, М. М. (2023). ЛЕКАРСТВЕННЫЕ РАСТЕНИЯ РОДА FERULA КАШКАДАРЬИНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ И ИХ ЗАЩИТА ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬСТВОМ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН. Биология и интегративная медицина, (4 (63)), 196-202.
7. Манноновна, А. М. (2022). Лекарственное Поражение Печени И Применение Гепатопротекторов При Этой Патологии. Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 3(4), 294-300.
8. Джалолов, Ф. Ф. (2021). Причины низкого усвоения знаний в общеобразовательных средних школах. Среднеевропейский научный вестник», журнал импакт-фактора, 11.
9. ISSN, R. S. A. 2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue 3, Mar., 2022 Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. ISSN, Rustamova Shahnoza Aripovna, 2776-0979.
10. Rustamova, S. A., & Shaxzoda, S. (2023). THE VALUE OF COMMUNICATION IN STUDENTS FORMING CULTURE HISTORICAL BASES. " GERMANY" MODERN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH: ACHIEVEMENTS, INNOVATIONS AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS, 9(1).
11. Sh, B. P. (2021). Ideas of Mahmudhoja Behbudi Reflected in Publicism. JournalNX, 7(10), 112-115.
12. Tagayeva, T., & Amanova, S. (2024, April). STYLISTIC PECULIARITIES OF LITERARY TEXT IN CREATIVE WORKS OF BERNARD SHAW. In Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit (pp. 520-524).
13. Tagayeva, T., & Kabridinova, K. (2024, April). INDIVIDUAL FEATURES OF ARTISTIC STYLE OF WM THACKERAY. In Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit (pp. 543-546).
14. Abdullayeva, N. K., & Bakhshilloyeva, N. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS'PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATION. Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal, 2(6), 19-28.
15. Shodiyeva, G. (2024). O 'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILIDA SO 'ZLARNI TURKUMLARGA AJRATISH MASALALARI. Interpretation and researches, (4 (26)).
16. qizi Tursunova, M. A., & qizi Shodieva, G. N. (2023). MAIN INFLUENTIAL FACTORS TO LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(3 SPECIAL), 1181-1183.
17. Aliyeva, N., & qizi Shodiyeva, G. N. (2023). Ingliz Tilida So 'Z Turkumlari Tasnifi Masalalari Sharhi. Scholar, 1(13), 22-27.

18. Shodieva, G. (2023). TRANSPOSITION OF WORD CATEGORIES IN UZBEK. Results of National Scientific Research International Journal, 2(4), 40-46.
19. Yusupova, S. A. Z., & kizi Shodieva, G. N. (2023). SOME ASPECTS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(1), 300-304.
20. Tursunova, M., & Qizi, S. G. N. (2023). NAVIGATING ETHICAL DILEMMAS IN BUSINESS DISCOURSE: AN EXPLORATION OF DISCOURSE ETHICS. Science and innovation, 2(Special Issue 5), 687-690.

